

Synthesis of some New Potential Antibacterials. Part-I

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Pyrazole and pyrazolin-5-one represent very important classes of heterocyclic compounds possessing a wide spectrum of biological activities¹. Besides, the traditional interest in pyrazole derivatives which have been the basis of numerous dyes and drugs, a number of substituted pyrazoles are used as antidiabetic and antineoplastic agents². In this respect sulphonamides based on pyrazole nucleus are of special interest, e.g. the common sulpha drug, orisul [1-phenyl-4-sulphonamoyl-(4'-amino)pyrazole] has prolonged bacteriostatic action *in vivo*³. Also incorporation of hydrazono⁴/azo⁵ group enhances the biological activity of heterocycles. Keeping in view the above, it was considered worthwhile to prepare derivatives of sulphonamides having pyrazoles/pyrazolin-5-ones linked by an azo/hydrazono grouping.

The sulphonamoylarylazopyrazoles (3) have been synthesised by reacting 3-sulphonamoylaryldiazono-4-phenylbutane-2,4-dione (1) with phenyl hydrazine and sulphonamoylaryldiazonopyrazolin-5-one (4) have been prepared by reacting 2-sulphonamoylaryldiazonobutyrate-1,3-dione (2) with semicarbazide hydrochloride (Scheme 1)

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian 270 MHz using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. M.ps. are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel G plates.

Scheme 1 Reagents (i) CH₃COCH₂COC₆H₅, CH₃COONa, (ii) CH₃COCH₂COEt, CH₃COONa, (iii) C₆H₅NHNH₂, CH₃COOH and (iv) H₂NCONHNH₂ HCl, CH₃COOH

3-Sulphonamoylphenylhydrazono-4-phenylbutan-2,4-dione (1): Sulphanilamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of conc. HCl (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To this, cold solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g) in water was added. The diazonium compound so obtained was filtered into already ice-cooled solution mixture

of sodium acetate (10 g) and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione (0.01 mol) in ethanol. The resulting solid was washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol to yield **1a** (70%), m.p. 123° (Found : C, 55.32; H, 4.10; N, 12.30. $C_{16}H_{15}O_4N_3S$ calcd. for : C, 55.65, H, 4.34; N, 12.17%); ν_{max} 3 220 (NH), 1 640 (CO involved in H-bonding), 1 520 (NH-N=C), 1 130 (SO₂), 755 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); δ 2.6 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.2–8.1 (9H, m, substituted phenyl), 13.3 (1H, s, NH H-bonded). Similarly, other compounds (yields 40–60%) were synthesised : **1b**, m.p. 203°; **c**, 186°; **d**, 222°; **e**, 68°; **f**, 50°; **g**, 87°; **h**, 196°.

2-Sulphonamoylphenylhydrazonobutyrate-1,3-dione (2) :

It was synthesised by the method similar to compound **1** except that ethyl acetoacetate was taken in place of phenyl-1,3-butanedione for coupling the diazonium salt of sulphadiazine. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give **2a** (65%), m.p. 124° (Found : C, 47.7; H, 4.54; N, 22.21. $C_{13}H_{17}N_5O_5S$ calcd. for : C, 47.94; H, 4.78; N, 22.71%); ν_{max} 3 310 (NH), 1 730, 1 670 (CO involved in hydrogen bonding), 1 110 (SO₂); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.55 (3H, s, COCH₃), 1.35 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.30 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, COOCH₂), 14.70 (1H, s, NH hydrogen bonded), 7.20–8.10 (4H, m, substituted phenyl). Similarly, other compounds were prepared : **2b**, m.p. 172°; **c**, 160°; **d**, 159°; **e**, 169°; **f**, 160°; **g**, 148°; **h**, 190°; **i**, 137°; **j**, 71°; **k**, 142°.

1-Phenyl-3-phenyl-5-methyl-4-(4'-sulphonamoylphenyl)azopyrazole (3) : Compound **1** (0.001 mol) dissolved in acetic acid (10–15 ml) was added to a solution of phenylhydrazine (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. On cooling, shining yellow crystals were obtained which were recrystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 226° (Found : C, 63.10; H, 4.23; N, 16.51. $C_{22}H_{19}N_5O_2S$ calcd. for : C, 63.30; H, 4.5; N, 16.78%); ν_{max} 3 290 (NH), 1 150 (SO₂), 1 510 (N=H), 2 950 (CH₃)

and 750 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); δ 2.50 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2–8.1 (14H, m, substituted phenyl), 8.8 (2H, s, NH₂). Similarly other compounds were synthesised : **3b**, m.p. 192°; **c**, 140°; **d**, 90°; **e**, 110°; **f**, 170°.

1-Carbamoyl-4-sulphonamoylphenylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-on (4) : 2-Sulphonamoylphenylhydrazonobutyrate-1,3-dione (0.001 mol) dissolved in acetic acid (15 ml) was added to a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.001 mol) in water and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h and then left overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give **4a** (60%), m.p. 232° (Found : C, 39.47; H, 3.82; N, 29.12. $C_{12}H_{14}N_8O_4S$ calcd. for : C, 39.34; H, 3.82; N, 30.60%); ν_{max} 3 220 (NH), 1 685 (CO), 1 520 (NH-N=C), 1 130 (SO₂), 750 (substituted phenyl); δ 2.30 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1–8.2 (4H, m, substituted phenyl), 9.2 (2H, s, NH₂), 12.3 (1H, s, NH). Similarly, other compounds were prepared : **4b**, m.p. 271°; **c**, 270°; **d**, 209°; **e**, 270°; **f**, 259°; **g**, 240°; **h**, 221°; **i**, 205°.

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